

**BASIC CONCEPTS OF FAMILY PSYCHOLOGY AND OVERCOMING
PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEMS**

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Abstract. *This article presents information about the importance of family psychology in society and the social functions of the family, based on research on the importance of family psychology. The main concepts of family psychology are the main research topics, which are devoted to the analysis of the typology and functions of modern families. At the same time, the article also touches on the psychological levels of families according to their functional capabilities and the specific manifestations of the formation of dysfunctional families. Also, the results of research on family psychology, based on the methods used in research on the psychological approach, are presented.*

Keywords: *Family, family psychology, psychology, upbringing, education, perfect person, spiritual maturity, mental state, psychological interview.*

Introduction

Family psychology is a branch of psychology that studies the relationships between family members, the systems of influence on them, and the problems and crises in the family. This field studies, analyzes, and helps relationships between people in the family, including the relationships between parents and children and siblings. Family psychology uses applied research to analyze family problems and crises, strengthen relationships between family members, and help family members become better. Initially, the focus on the child's problem gradually shifts to the client's personal problems. However, it cannot be said that such a problem or situation, which the psychologist understands well, is clearly understood by the parents themselves. Therefore, it is advisable for the client to feel and understand the real reason for his appeal to the psychologist. In this area, topics such as communication between family members, well-being in the family, mutual

assistance and support, problem solving, methods of upbringing and education are studied. Family psychology helps to prevent problematic situations in the upbringing of children in the family, in the growth of the younger generation as educated, spiritual and mature people. Another important function of the family is the function of upbringing. The foundation for the mental, physical, moral, and aesthetic education of children is laid in the family. The family is responsible not only for laying the foundation of the building called a person, but also for its completion until the last brick is laid. Parents are artists, children are works of art, and the process of upbringing is art itself. The formation and upbringing of a full-fledged citizen of society falls within the scope of this function of the modern family. Because the socialization of a person primarily takes place in the family. Through upbringing in the family, a certain political and ideological worldview, moral norms and behavioral patterns, and physical qualities are instilled in a person. Family psychology, as a science, studies the objective laws of the family's activity as a social institution, the mechanisms of family-marriage and kinship relations, and the manifestation of the social behavior of family members in specific situations related to lifestyle. As a practical branch of social psychology, it studies and studies the institutions of marriage, the specific aspects of relationships between family members - kindness, care, sympathy, solidarity, subordination, obedience, leadership, gender-specific laws of the distribution and interaction of family roles, the emotional and emotional connection between parents and children, close relatives, the course of psychological processes related to the organization of family life and lifestyle. The psychology of family life is thus a branch of science that studies how people interact with each other, live a family life together with good intentions, and live in harmony. When social psychology studies the psychology of the family, it views it as a part of society, a small social group. For this reason, specific research focuses on the factors underlying its emergence, existence, and circumstances surrounding its end. After all, although at first glance the relationships between family members seem to be based on emotional feelings, in fact the process of one person's liking for another, choosing, and living together is completely subject to socio-psychological laws. Some scientists, for example, the French researcher Le Ple, at one time suggested that in addition to purely psychological laws, the family is also a place of socio-economic laws, taking into account changes in household management and the family budget depending on the number and composition of children. In his opinion, family relationships are extremely changeable, and they undergo constant qualitative changes under the influence of time and era, depending on the number and quality of family members, and even the usual relationship between spouses can take on a different form under the pressure of the years, social norms, the development of industry, or the decline of spirituality. He

emphasizes that the system of parent-child relationships, including even the authority of the father, changes, and the psychological distance between close relatives increases with the passing of years. One of the important topics of family psychology is family structure and relationships. In this area, concepts such as relationships between family members, relationships between parents and children, men and women, relationships between siblings, the process of mutual support and mutual assistance of family members are studied. Psychologists have studied in great detail that the future of a child, his or her development as a person, largely depends on the parental family and the ideas formed in the child about it. Studies have shown that a child's ideas about his or her family often partially coincide with the ideas and reality of the parents. Usually, parents expect their child to understand this and always be grateful to them, but children have different ideas about this. One of the foundations of a child's experience is the social character that is formed in him under the influence of the parental family. That is, mutual trust, self-esteem, the main concept of family psychology are the qualities that are formed in the child's mind under the influence of his parents, brothers and sisters. If a child learns to live in peace and harmony, observing and imitating their parents' interactions throughout his life, then, looking at his brothers and sisters, he learns how to behave in complex situations of interaction in society, understands the meaning of life, and the formation of his worldview, secular and religious beliefs also occurs under the influence of these relationships. The relationship between husband and wife begins with adaptation, that is, a process of gradual getting used to and adapting to each other, because each of them enters a new environment, a new life with their own personal experience gained in their own family, their social ideas about the family. As a result, they begin to cultivate new qualities for new relationships, while giving up part of the experience they gained in their parents' family. They mainly studied the ethnopsychological aspects of family relations from the perspective of customs, traditions, and practices specific to the Uzbek family. However, the family institution studies the objective laws of the family's functioning as a social institution, the mechanisms of family-marriage and kinship relations, and the manifestation of social behavior of family members in specific situations related to lifestyle. As a practical branch of social psychology, it studies and studies the institutions of marriage, the specific aspects of relationships between family members - kindness, care, sympathy, solidarity, subordination, obedience, leadership, gender-related laws of the distribution of family roles and interaction, the emotional and emotional connection between parents and children, close relatives, the course of psychological processes related to the organization of family life and lifestyle. Analyzing the laws of family psychology as a social reality, we considered it appropriate to cite the data presented in numerous studies that focused on

the psychological nature, origin and dynamics of relationships inherent in family relationships. In this regard, we turn to the results of a number of studies that have studied the phenomenology of family psychological relations as an object of socio-psychological research. One of the most detailed monographic studies of socio-psychological relations in the family and the laws of their origin is the Russian scientist L.Ya. Gozman (1987). Based on these studies, it is advisable to provide young families with regular consultations on eliminating the problems that arise in the study of family psychology and to eliminate the problems by conducting psychological interviews every month. The characteristics identified with the help of psychodiagnostics, in most cases their predominantly negative aspects, should be eliminated through psychological correction work. It indicates certain qualities of the person being studied that may interfere with the proper implementation of certain activities, and provides psychological advice on how to eliminate them. When providing psychological advice, it is also possible to use information from a number of other scientific sources, the life experience of the psychologist, the responsible employee, professional skills, and other similar sources, but in this case, the decisive source should be the information obtained from the person being advised, the husband, wife, mother-in-law, daughter-in-law, child, young employee, etc., himself, using psychodiagnostics (conducting a psychological interview).

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that, based on advanced research on the study of family psychology, eliminating problems arising in the family, in child rearing, and in education will serve the future generation to grow up as physically healthy, spiritually mature people. It is not wrong to say that family well-being, family harmony, and child rearing are, first of all, a part of our society. By conducting psychological interviews based on family status, family psychologists eliminate the problems that have arisen and further strengthen the mental state, spiritual state, and intellectual development of family members.

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